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Can The Performance of Millennial Employees Based on Emotional Intelligence Can Be Mediated By Work Life Balance ? (Study of Jabodetabek Employees)

Dellia Mila Vernia¹

¹University Indraprasta PGRI of Jakarta,
 Email: delliamilavernia@gmail.com

Abstract

In the midst of a global pandemic that has spread throughout the world at the beginning of 2020, it has had an impact on all lines of life, such as the health sector, education sector and the economic sector. The Covid 19 pandemic outbreak has completely restructured work organizations, this unexpected change has forced workers to adjust their work schedules so they can complete all responsibilities at home, to get maximum performance. Improving employee performance is an important requirement in achieving organizational goals and producing superior quality products and/or services. So that employees are expected to be able to balance work and home life, because during the Covid 19 pandemic, all work activities and personal life are centered at home. Therefore, there is a need for regularity between work tasks and housework. So, an employee must be able to create a work life balance. Respondents in this research were 200 employees who filled out a questionnaire via survey using the SEM PLS method. The results of the research state that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on work life balance, emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance, work life balance has a significant effect on performance, and emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance mediated by work life balance.

Keywords: *Performance, Emotional intelligence, Work Life Balance*

Abstrak

Ditengah global pandemic yang telah tersebar seluruh dunia pada awal tahun 2020 memberikan pengaruhnya keseluruh lini kehidupan, seperti bidang kesehatan, bidang pendidikan dan bidang ekonomi. Wabah pandemic covid 19 ini telah merestrukturisasi organisasi kerja secara total, perubahan tak terduga ini telah memaksa pekerja, untuk menyesuaikan jadwal kerja agar dapat menyelesaikan semua tanggung jawab yang ada di rumah, untuk mendapatkan kinerja maksimal. Meningkatkan kinerja karyawan merupakan persyaratan penting dalam mencapai tujuan organisasi dan menghasilkan produk dan atau jasa unggulan yang berkualitas. Sehingga para karyawan diharapkan dapat dapat menyeimbangkan pekerjaan dan kehidupan rumah tangga, karena dimasa pandemic covid 19, segala aktivitas pekerjaan dan kehidupan pribadi dipusatkan di rumah. Oleh karena itu dibutuhkan keteraturan antara tugas pekerjaan dengan pekerjaan rumah. Sehingga, seorang karyawan harus dapat menciptakan *work life balance*.—Responden dalam penelitian ini sebanyak 200 karyawan yang mengisi angket melalui survei dengan menggunakan metode SEM PLS. Hasil penelitian menyatakan bahwa *emotional intelligence* berpengaruh signifikan terhadap *work life balance*, *emotional intelligence* berpengaruh signifikan terhadap kinerja., *work life balance* berpengaruh signifikan terhadap kinerja, dan *emotional intelligence* berpengaruh signifikan terhadap kinerja dengan dimediasi *work life balance*.

Kata kunci: *Performance, Emotional intelligence, Work Life Balance*

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PENDAHULUAN

In January 2020, WHO declared a new viral disease, known as Covid 19, a global public health emergency. The World Health Organization stated that the spread of Covid 19 in various countries throughout the world had a high risk, until finally in March 2020, WHO gave the lower category of Covid 19 as a disease outbreak that appeared throughout the world (basak). As of May 1 2020, more than 3.27 million cases of Covid-19 have been recorded in 187 countries and territories and resulted in more than 234,505 deaths. The concept of social distancing is needed when implementing working from home, known as WFH. Working from home is where individuals do work from home using digital platforms, and this business trend

is changing which opens up challenges for the business sector which are challenges that have never existed before. In the midst of the Covid 19 pandemic, business operations are still running, employees can access them using digital platforms. This has a negative impact on business organizations and the economy, forcing companies to carry out operations remotely using digital technology (Kaushik & Guleria, 2020).

One of the generations in the workplace today is the millennial generation, the largest workforce currently available. So, it is important to understand issues about millennials that can have an impact on their performance in the workplace, such as the influence of technology, cultural changes, understanding their motivation and the appreciation they receive for the performance they have produced (Darby & Morrell, 2019). Employees born in 1981-2000 are millennials who prioritize welfare. This generation is called generation Y which has differences from previous generations in terms of work values, work attitudes, expectations and preferences for work. This is a challenge in itself to get good performance in the company (He et al., 2019).

The Covid 19 pandemic outbreak has completely restructured work organizations, this unexpected change has forced workers to adjust work schedules so they can complete all responsibilities at home, of course this is different from workers who live alone or without children. Workers with parental responsibilities are suddenly personally involved with childcare throughout the day, workspaces filled with discomfort, and loss of privacy, impact employee performance. This has new problems in getting maximum performance in the era of the Covid 19 pandemic (Costa et al., 2022).

Sumber: databoks.katadata.co.id

Coronavirus 19 also poses a threat to mental health and emotional well-being. Since the start of the pandemic, there has been an increase in mental health problems including stress, depression and anxiety disorders. As increasing evidence points to worsening psychiatric outcomes, given that the negative emotions generated by the pandemic are likely to play a central role in mood and anxiety disorders, one of the factors that provides psychological resilience is a set of skills, abilities and competencies known as emotional intelligence (Persich et al., 2021).

Covid 19 has also pushed work and home life under one roof for many families, and it takes a struggle to manage it all. Schools and daycares are closed, work cannot continue in offices because they have to use technology so they can work remotely. On the one hand, the level of disease transmission, increasing workload and the emergence of anxiety and fear have resulted in disrupting work-life balance for workers. Of course, this also has a negative impact on health, performance, competence and mental health during the pandemic (Yayla & Eskici İlgin, 2021)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Covid 19

Since the discovery of the corona virus, scientists have debated its origins. The world is living in the shadow of Covid 19, globally at the end of January 2021, 99 million cases of Covid 19 were confirmed, including 2 million deaths, which had been reported to WHO. Humans are facing a health crisis that is triggering a socio-economic crisis (Tu et al., 2021). Pandemic comes from Greek, which means all and people. This term is used by disease experts when epidemics develop in different countries and continents simultaneously. WHO describes a pandemic as a new outbreak that spreads easily from person to person throughout the world. So, a disease outbreak is when a pandemic is widespread, over several countries or continents, usually affecting a large number of people. An epidemic is an event where a disease spreads actively, out of control but often within one country or location. In contrast, a pandemic is an epidemic on a much larger geographic scale and affects a large number of people (Shlomo & Barzani, 2020).

Millennials

Categorized as people born between 1980 and 2001, millennials have several positive characteristics such as multitasking, working in teams, connection to community tasks, and optimism (Alsop, 2008). Apart from that, as talented and highly educated people, millennials also have an orientation towards achieving achievement. In contrast, a number of studies categorize millennials as an entitled generation that lacks experience, sweat equity, and the desire to maintain a long career at any company. In addition, the millennial generation is considered as individuals who are inexperienced and have a high level of intelligence, who have expectations of receiving immediate rewards (de Hauw & de Vos, 2010)

Performance

Performance is an important understanding for individuals who make valuable contributions to the organization (Campbell, 2012). According to (Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009) employee performance is an important factor in determining company performance. So individual performance is the ability of an individual to carry out work tasks by having the necessary skills, experience, attitudes and motivation. According to (Linda Koopmans, 2014) defines individual performance as employee behavior or actions compared to the results of these actions. Employees can improve organizational performance by generating ideas using the foundation in creating new products, services and work processes, so that performance triggers various fields for conducting research, such as management, occupational health, occupational and organizational psychology. In line with (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000) also states that performance is an action, behavior and results of employees involved aimed at achieving organizational goals. According to (Sahakiant, 2015) performance is influenced by three factors, namely environmental factors (economic, demographic, social and cultural), internal organizational factors (organizational policies, leadership, raw materials), individual employee factors (psychological and cognitive aspects). In realizing performance then you must be able to see individual actions in helping the organization achieve its goals (Moorman, Robert et al., 1998).

Work Life Balance

(Frone, 2003) argues that initially, work life balance was a literature that developed from a lack of conflict. As for ideas related to effectiveness and satisfaction in the work and family domains that are consistent with a person's values or priorities (Greenhaus & Powell, 2003). Life domains are defined as three separate domains namely work, family and personal. Work life balance is defined as an overall assessment of an individual's effectiveness and satisfaction in work and family roles that are consistent with life values at the same time (Greenhaus & Powell, 2003). According to (Wayne et al., 2017) balance is consistent with individual values, which implies that balance itself is determined by the individual. Thus, balance is not defined as equality between work, family and life domains but by the desired balance between domains at any time in an individual's life and career. (Greenhaus & Powell, 2003) defines work family balance as the extent to which an individual believes that effectiveness and satisfaction come from two domains.

The definition of work life balance according to (Haar et al., 2013) is as an individual's perception of the good role of life balance. Work life balance is a major concern for employees, organizations and society throughout the world (Valcour, 2007). Although responsibility towards personal, family and social roles in life is very important, employees often dedicate their roles to diverse work demands (Poulose & Dhal, 2020). Several previous studies have identified that one of the causes of employees' lack of commitment is due to an increase in the balance of work and family in work settings. Work life balance is an important component of job quality. All of these definitions reveal that work life balance is related to the work and life of employees in order to achieve balance and harmony (Tamunomiebi & Oyibo, 2020).

Emotional intelligence

Emotional intelligence was conceptualized by (Thorndike EL., 1920) then developed into the theory of multiple intelligence (Gardner, 1983) which states that the construction of emotional intelligence consists of interpersonal intelligence which refers to knowledge about a person's internal aspects, and the ability to notice differences between other people in their lives. matters of mood, emotion, motivation and intention. Emotional intelligence according to (Salovey & Mayer, 1990) is the ability to understand one's own and other people's emotions, to differentiate between positive and negative effects of emotions and to use emotional information to influence thinking and behavior. Furthermore, (Goleman, 1995) identified emotional intelligence as the ability to face, identify, understand and express emotions. It refers to how emotions are applied in practical thinking and reasoning, and the positive regulation of emotions. Emotional intelligence can be identified as a personal quality that can positively interact and influence daily life (Morehouse, 2007).

(Goleman, 1995) argues that the emotional intelligence dimension consists of (a) self-regulation which is guided by the learning produced to achieve goals. Self-regulation or self-management is a core competency which can be interpreted as the ability to remain calm in conditions of conflict and then (b) self-awareness is self-awareness as the ability to recognize one's feelings (c) self-motivation is self-action carried out daily which has a specific purpose by taking responsibility at work (d) social skills refer to a person's talent in managing relationships with other people or also called skills consisting of respect, commitment, openness, tolerance, empathy, communication.

Relationship Between Variables

a. Emotional intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance

With emotional intelligence, a person has better strength to achieve performance in the workplace. Emotional intelligence has a role in improving the effectiveness of management, training and organizational performance. This is also supported by research (Iqbal et al., 2021) which states that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance. Research states that students who have high emotional intelligence have good performance. Therefore, it is very important to conduct research on emotional intelligence on employee performance. Meanwhile, (Gryn, 2010) states that there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and employee performance.

b. Emotional intelligence has a positive effect on work life balance

Various studies state that emotional intelligence has a significant impact on maintaining balance in professional and personal life (Grandey, 2000). Someone who has high emotional intelligence will be able to manage the domain of life and work efficiently. So this ability helps employees to maintain work life balance (Shylaja & Prasad, 2017).

Developing an individual's work-life balance is very important (Koubova & Buchko, 2013). In line with this, research conducted by (Gupta, 2016) shows that EI has a negative relationship with family role conflicts that interfere with work and also family role conflicts that interfere with work. A number of other studies clearly show that EI is positively and significantly related to WLB (Applewhite, 2018; Kumarasamy et al., 2016). Based on these studies, it can be said that in an organization, employees' EI has an impact on their WLB. Therefore, the following proposition can be put forward:

c. Work life balance has a positive effect on employee performance

There are three main problems related to work life imbalance which is influenced by technology, shifts in the nature of work activities, especially tasks related to technology which require updating field knowledge and further related to job demands (R. Helmle et al., 2014). According to (Obiageli & Ngozi, 2015), work life balance is important in influencing employee performance. This research is in line with (Soomro et al., 2018), which states that work life balance has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

d. Emotional intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance which is mediated by work life balance

Emotional intelligence is one of the factors that can influence work life balance (Goleman, 2009). It is very important to have emotional intelligence in work life balance because it allows someone to act and think to gain maturity to think from a positive perspective. However, only a few empirical studies discuss the relationship between emotional intelligence and work life balance, one of which is Jyothi (2012) who found that emotional intelligence plays an important role in the work life balance of female employees. Based on several research results, it is stated that work life balance has a positive effect on employee performance and work life imbalance has also been proven to have an influence on employee welfare (Dinah, 2020).

Conceptual frame

Research Hypothesis

Based on the problem formulation that has been described, the next step is to formulate a research hypothesis. The formulation of the research hypothesis in this study is as follows:

a. Emotional Intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance

b. Emotional Intelligence has a positive effect on work life balance

c. Work life balance has a positive effect on employee performance

d. Emotional Intelligence has a positive effect on employee performance which is mediated by work life balance

RESEARCH METHODS

In this research, the method used is the analysis method with the PLS approach. This research study is based on primary data using an online questionnaire. The main topic of discussion in this research is the millennial employee performance model based on emotional intelligence mediated by work life balance. The respondents in this research were 200 millennial employees in the Jabodetabek area who filled out a questionnaire via Google Form.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Verification Statistical Analysis

This verification analysis is related to the formation of a structural equation model, which will then be tested using the PLS-SEM method. According to Hair et al (2019), the PLS-SEM method estimates complex models with many constructs, indicator variables and structural paths without imposing distributional assumptions on the data. The PLS-SEM model calculation process is carried out using the help of the SmartPLS 3.0 program application.

Outer Model Testing (Measurement Model)

a. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is testing construct validity. An indicator is said to have good validity if it has a loading factor value greater than 0.70 (Hair et al, 2017a). Based on the estimation results using the help of the SmartPLS 3 program application, the initial model test output was obtained as follows.

Source: Processing data (2021)

Fig. 4.2 Diagram Nilai Loading Factor Evaluasi Outer Model

Based on the test results with SmartPLS 3.0, the following results were obtained.

Tabel 41 Loading Factor

Construk	Loading Factor	R kritis	Kriteria (Loading Factor \geq 0,70)
EI10 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,831	0,70	Valid
EI11 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,722	0,70	Valid
EI12 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,757	0,70	Valid
EI13 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,785	0,70	Valid
EI14 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,736	0,70	Valid
EI15 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,797	0,70	Valid
EI16 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,755	0,70	Valid
EI17 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,759	0,70	Valid
EI18 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,656	0,70	Valid
EI19 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,789	0,70	Valid
EI2 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,743	0,70	Valid
EI20 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,782	0,70	Valid

Construk	Loading Factor	R kritis	Kriteria (Loading Factor ≥ 0.70)
EI21 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,823	0,70	Valid
EI22 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,807	0,70	Valid
EI23 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,804	0,70	Valid
EI3 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,587	0,70	Valid
EI4 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,765	0,70	Valid
EI5 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,603	0,70	Valid
EI6 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,818	0,70	Valid
EI7 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,687	0,70	Valid
EI8 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,752	0,70	Valid
EI9 <- Emotional Intelligence	0,756	0,70	Valid
KIN1 <- Performance	0,779	0,70	Valid
KIN10 <- Performance	0,846	0,70	Valid
KIN11 <- Performance	0,849	0,70	Valid
KIN12 <- Performance	0,867	0,70	Valid
KIN13 <- Performance	0,820	0,70	Valid
KIN14 <- Performance	0,869	0,70	Valid
KIN15 <- Performance	0,727	0,70	Valid
KIN16 <- Performance	0,780	0,70	Valid
KIN2 <- Performance	0,865	0,70	Valid
KIN3 <- Performance	0,836	0,70	Valid
KIN4 <- Performance	0,845	0,70	Valid
KIN5 <- Performance	0,866	0,70	Valid
KIN6 <- Performance	0,897	0,70	Valid
KIN7 <- Performance	0,885	0,70	Valid
KIN8 <- Performance	0,868	0,70	Valid
KIN9 <- Performance	0,892	0,70	Valid
WLB1 <- Work Life Balance	0,820	0,70	Valid
WLB2 <- Work Life Balance	0,875	0,70	Valid
WLB3 <- Work Life Balance	0,844	0,70	Valid
WLB4 <- Work Life Balance	0,826	0,70	Valid
WLB5 <- Work Life Balance	0,796	0,70	Valid
WLB6 <- Work Life Balance	0,818	0,70	Valid

Source: Processing data (2021)

Table 1 shows the loading factor values for each construct for each variable. Based on this table, it can be seen that all loading factors have a value of more than 0.70. So it can be concluded that based on each construct in the research it has good validity. Next, average variance extracted (AVE) testing will be carried out to further strengthen the results of convergent validity with the criterion that if the AVE value is > 0.5 (Hair et al, 2019), then the construct used in the research is valid. The following are the results of the average variance extracted test using the PLS 3.0 program:

Table 2 Average Variance Extracted

Laten	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	R kritis	Kriteria (AVE ≥ 0.5)

<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	0,560	0,5	Valid
Performance	0,713	0,5	Valid
<i>Work Life Balance</i>	0,689	0,5	Valid

Source: Processing data (2021)

Based on Table 4.2, the convergent validity results can be seen based on the average variance extracted value. These results show that all latent variables have an AVE value of more than 0.5. This indicates that the indicators that form the latent construct have good convergent validity when seen from the average variance extracted value.

b. Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity can be seen from the cross loading value. Fornell and Larcker (1981) in Ghazali (2014:45) stated that the correlation value of indicators with their constructs must be greater than the correlation values between indicators and other constructs. Below are presented the results of the discriminant validity test using the Smart PLS 3.0 program.

Table 3 Cross Loading Discriminant Validity Test Values

	Emotional Intelligence	Performance	Work Life Balance
EI10	0,831	0,642	0,226
EI11	0,722	0,567	0,133
EI12	0,757	0,564	0,133
EI13	0,785	0,615	0,198
EI14	0,736	0,526	0,107
EI15	0,797	0,634	0,255
EI16	0,755	0,550	0,285
EI17	0,759	0,632	0,300
EI18	0,656	0,399	-0,012
EI19	0,789	0,641	0,174
EI2	0,743	0,553	0,097
EI20	0,782	0,552	0,089
EI21	0,823	0,605	0,172
EI22	0,807	0,561	0,145
EI23	0,804	0,713	0,293
EI3	0,587	0,385	0,293
EI4	0,765	0,543	0,186
EI5	0,603	0,393	0,185
EI6	0,818	0,584	0,218
EI7	0,687	0,487	0,179
EI8	0,752	0,583	0,207
EI9	0,756	0,661	0,217
KIN1	0,578	0,779	0,319
KIN10	0,628	0,846	0,277
KIN11	0,636	0,849	0,228
KIN12	0,617	0,867	0,270
KIN13	0,608	0,820	0,313
KIN14	0,649	0,869	0,276
KIN15	0,586	0,727	0,182
KIN16	0,701	0,780	0,135
KIN2	0,672	0,865	0,296

	Emotional Intelligence	Performance	Work Life Balance
KIN3	0,639	0,836	0,323
KIN4	0,624	0,845	0,302
KIN5	0,656	0,866	0,237
KIN6	0,695	0,897	0,273
KIN7	0,682	0,885	0,328
KIN8	0,592	0,868	0,283
KIN9	0,665	0,892	0,237
WLB1	0,267	0,271	0,820
WLB2	0,246	0,281	0,875
WLB3	0,242	0,262	0,844
WLB4	0,188	0,289	0,826
WLB5	0,175	0,239	0,796
WLB6	0,163	0,226	0,818
EI1	0,633	0,481	0,308

Sumber: Pengolahan Data (2021)

Based on Table 4.3, it can be seen that all indicators have a high correlation with their constructs compared to other constructs. So it can be concluded that the research model has good discriminant validity in cross loading discriminant validity.

c. Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability to determine whether the construct reliability is good or not. Each construct is said to be reliable if it has a Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability that is greater than 0.70 (Hair et al, 2017). Below are presented the results of the reliability test using the Smart PLS 3.0 program.

Table 4 score Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Latent	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	0,964	0,967
Performance	0,973	0,975
<i>Work Life Balance</i>	0,910	0,930

Source: Processing data (2021)

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that there is a latent construct that has a Cronbach's alpha value of more than 0.7, this indicates that the latent construct has good reliability. Apart from that, the composite reliability value of all latent constructs also has a value greater than 0.70. Based on the Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values obtained, it shows that the model has good reliability.

Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

Inner model evaluation is an analysis of the results of the relationship between constructs. Inner model testing consists of R square, f square, Q-square predictive relevance, and hypothesis testing. Inner model testing is carried out to determine the significance between the independent variables and the dependent variable and to find out how much influence the variables have. The results of the inner model testing are described in the structural model as follows:

a. R Square

Furthermore, based on the test results with SmartPLS 3., the R Square results were obtained as follows.

Tabel 5 R Square

	R Square	Kuat Hubungan
Performance	0,591	Moderat
<i>Work Life Balance</i>	0,068	Lemah

Source: Processing data (2021)

According to Chin (1998) in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011:21), R Square Adjusted with a value of 0.67 indicates a strong model, a value of 0.33 indicates a moderate model and a value of 0.19 indicates a weak model. From the results of Table 4.3, it can be seen that the R-Square for the Performance variable is 0.591, which means that Emotional Intelligence mediated by Work Life Balance contributes an influence of 0.591 or 59.1% to Performance. Meanwhile, the remaining 40.9% is the influence of other unobserved factors. The R-Square for the Work Life Balance variable is 0.068, which means that Emotional Intelligence contributes an influence of 0.068 or 6.8% to Work Life Balance. Meanwhile, the remaining 93.2% is the influence of other unobserved factors.

b. f Square

Next is to look at the f Square value. An f Square value of 0.02 indicates a small rating, an Effect Size of 0.15 indicates a medium rating and an Effect Size of 0.35 indicates a large rating (Cohen, 1988 in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011:21). Based on the test results with SmartPLS 3, the F Square results were obtained as follows.

Table 46 f Square

Variabel	Effect Size	Rating
Kinerja		
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	1,201	Besar
<i>Work Life Balance</i>	0,037	Kecil
<i>Work Life Balance</i>		
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	0,073	Kecil

Source: Processing data (2021)

Based on Table 4.6, it shows that the Emotional Intelligence and Work Life Balance variables have an influence in categories that are included in the large and small categories, the Emotional Intelligence variable has an influence that is included in the small category in influencing Work Life Balance.

c. Q² Predictive Relevance

The Q-square test is used to measure how well the observation values produced by the model and also the parameter estimates are. A Q-square value greater than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has a predictive relevance value, while a Q-square value of less than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has less predictive relevance (Cohen, 1988 in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011:21). The Q-square value obtained by using the R² value in the table above, obtained the following calculation results:

Table 47 Q² Predictive Relevance

Variabel	R Square	1-R Square
Performance	0,591	0,409
<i>Work Life Balance</i>	0,068	0,932
Q ² =	$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R_1^2) (1 - R_2^2) = 0,35$	
Galat =	$Q^2 = 100\% - 35\% = 65\%$	

Source: Processing data (2021)

Based on the calculation results above, it is known that the Q square value is greater than 0, this means that the observed values have been reconstructed well so that the model has predictive relevance. This means that there is 0.350 or 35.0% of the relative influence of the structural model on the observation measurements for endogenous latent variables, and as much as 65% is model error.

Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using the path coefficient, t-value and p-value. To assess the significance and predictions in hypothesis testing, it can be seen from the path coefficient and t-value (Kock, N. 2016). According to Kock, N (2016) assessing predictions and significance in hypothesis testing can be seen by p-value. The t-table values can be seen in the following table.

Table 8 Nilai T-tabel

	<i>One tailed</i>	<i>Two tailed</i>
t-tabel	1.64	1.96

Sorce: Abdillah & Hartono (2015: 211)

According to Kock, N. (2016), with a confidence level of 95% (alpha 5%), two tailed, the following t-table values are obtained:

1. If the t-statistic value is > 1.96 (used for direct influence), then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.
2. If the t-statistic value is < 1.96 (used for direct influence), then H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected.

The magnitude of the significance value between the variables being tested is presented in the form of a value contained in an arrow that connects one variable to the target variable.

The Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Work Life Balance.

Research hypothesis 1 states that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on Work Life Balance. And from this hypothesis it was developed into a statistical hypothesis as follows:

H_0 : Emotional Intelligence has no significant effect on Work Life Balance;

H_1 : Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on Work Life Balance.

Next, based on the hypothesis above, a hypothesis test was carried out using the bootstrapping method using SmartPLS software, and the following values were obtained:

Table 9 Path coefficient and t-count of the Influence of Emotional Intelligence towards Work Life Balance

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>t-Statistik</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Result
<i>Emotional Intelligence terhadap Work Life Balance</i>	0,262	4,236	0,000	rejected H_0

From the results of Table 4.9 above, the Original Sample (O) value is 0.262, indicating that the direction of influence of emotional intelligence on Work Life Balance is positive or in the same direction, meaning that if emotional intelligence increases or gets better, work life balance will increase or get better too. The influence of emotional intelligence on work life balance is significant, with a t-statistic value of 4.236 which is greater than the t table or $4.236 > 1.96$, and a p value of 0.000 which is smaller than alpha 5% (0.05). Thus, H_1 is accepted, meaning that Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on Work Life Balance.

Effect of Work Life Balance on Performance

Research hypothesis 2 states that work life balance has a significant effect on performance. And from this hypothesis it was developed into a statistical hypothesis as follows:

H_0 : Work Life Balance has no significant effect on performance;

H_2 : Work Life Balance has a significant effect on performance.

Next, based on the hypothesis above, a hypothesis test was carried out using the bootstrapping method using SmartPLS software, and the following values were obtained:

Table 10 Path coefficients and t-calculations of the Effect of Work Life Balance on Performance

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>t-Statistik</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Kesimpulan
<i>Work Life Balance to Performance</i>	0,127	2,554	0,011	rejected H_0

From the results of Table 4.10 above, the Original Sample (O) value is 0.127, indicating that the direction of influence of Work Life Balance on Performance is positive or in the same direction, meaning that if Work Life Balance increases or gets better, Performance will increase or get better too. The influence of Work Life Balance on Performance is significant, with a t-statistic value of 2.554 which is greater than the t table or $2.554 > 1.96$, and a p value of 0.011 which is smaller than alpha 5% (0.05). Thus, H2 is accepted, meaning that Work Life Balance has a significant effect on performance.

The influence of emotional intelligence on performance

Research hypothesis 3 states that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance. And from this hypothesis it was developed into a statistical hypothesis as follows:

H0: Emotional intelligence has no significant effect on performance;

H3: Emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance.

Next, based on the hypothesis above, a hypothesis test was carried out using the bootstrapping method using SmartPLS software, and the following values were obtained:

Table 11 Path coefficients and t-calculations of the Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Performance

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>t-Statistik</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Kesimpulan</i>
<i>Emotional Intelligence to performance</i>	0,726	16,752	0,000	Tolak H ₀

From the results of Table 4.11 above, the Original Sample (O) value is 0.726, indicating that the direction of influence of emotional intelligence on performance is positive or in the same direction, meaning that if emotional intelligence increases or gets better, performance will increase or get better too. The influence of emotional intelligence on performance is significant, with a t-statistic value of 16.752 which is greater than the t table or $16.752 > 1.96$, and a p value of 0.000 which is smaller than alpha 5% (0.05). Thus, H3 is accepted, meaning that Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on performance.

The influence of Emotional Intelligence on Performance mediated by Work Life Balance

Research hypothesis 4 states that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance mediated by Work Life Balance. And from this hypothesis it was developed into a statistical hypothesis as follows:

H0: Emotional Intelligence has no significant effect on performance mediated by Work Life Balance;

H4: Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on performance mediated by Work Life Balance.

Next, based on the hypothesis above, a hypothesis test was carried out using the bootstrapping method using SmartPLS software, and the following values were obtained:

Table 12 Path coefficients and t-calculation of the influence of Emotional Intelligence on Performance mediated by Work Life Balance

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>t-Statistik</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Kesimpulan</i>
<i>Emotional Intelligence to Performance mediated by Work Life Balance</i>	0,033	2,197	0,028	Tolak H ₀

From the results of Table 4.12 above, the Original Sample (O) value is 0.033, indicating that the direction of influence of Emotional Intelligence on Performance mediated by Work Life Balance is in the same direction, meaning that Emotional Intelligence will cause Work Life Balance to get better, which in turn will improve or get better. Performance. The influence of Emotional Intelligence on Performance mediated by Work Life Balance is significant, with a t-statistic value of 2.197 which is greater than the t table or $2.197 > 1.96$, and a p value of 0.028 which is smaller than alpha 5% (0.05). Thus, H4 is accepted, meaning that Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on performance mediated by Work Life Balance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussions that have been carried out, the conclusions that can be drawn are as follows:

1. Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on Work Life Balance.
2. Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on performance.
3. Work Life Balance has a significant effect on performance.
4. Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on performance mediated by Work Life Balance.

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